

to foliage feeders. Seventy-two accessions of 13 wild species, one *O. sativa*/*O. nivara* hybrid, and an unknown *Oryza* sp. were resistant or

moderately resistant to leafhoppers and planthoppers. Thirteen accessions of eight wild species were resistant to multiple pests (Table 2). □

Resistance in different rice genetic lines to rice moth *Sitotroga cerealella* (Oliv.)

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We tested resistance in various rice lines in Pakistan to rice moth *S. cerealella* (Oliv.), an important storage pest of rice, wheat, and maize.

Rice moth was reared in the laboratory at 28 ± 3 °C and $63 \pm 4\%$ relative humidity. Rice grain also was conditioned at this temperature for a week. About 100 24-h-old eggs of the rice moth were placed on 30 g of conditioned grain. Larvae hatched and were allowed to complete their life cycle. Adult moths started emerging 25 d after infestation.

Infested grain was sieved through No. 20 mesh to separate the frass and food remains, weighed, and loss calculated. Total grains and number of damaged grains were counted and percent damaged grains calculated. The experiment was replicated three times. Moisture content of test lines ranged between 11.1 and 12.6%.

Genetic line 1017-6-B and OP62 showed significantly less grain loss (see table). Highest susceptibility was in line 4439 and Bas 385.

Grain weight was investigated as a possible source of resistance, but no relationship could be detected. Correlations between 1,000-grain weight and weight loss ($r = -0.32$), damaged grains ($r = -0.26$), and number of adults that emerged ($r = -0.31$) were negative. □

Dry weight loss, damaged grains, and number of *S. cerealella* adults that emerged in storage of different rice genetic lines of Pakistan.^a

Genetic line	Crown at ^b	Dry weight loss (%)	Damaged grains (%)	Adults (no.)
1017-6-B	NARC	0.3 a	0.2 a	5 a
OP62	KK	0.7 a	0.8 a	13 ab
OP61	KK	1.0 ab	1.2 bc	24 bc
IET4094	KK	1.2 ab	1.2 bc	27 cd
IR64	KK	2.1 bc	1.5 bcd	38 c-f
TN1	NIAB	2.3 bc	1.7 cde	34 c-f
DM24	NIAB	2.4 bc	1.8 c-f	40 def
OP57	KK	2.7 cd	1.99 c-f	47 efg
DM38	NIAB	2.9 cd	1.9 c-g	49 fg
OP53	KK	2.9 cd	2.0 c-g	51 fgh
OP54	KK	3.2 cde	2.2 d-h	60 ghi
DM25	NIAB	3.3 cde	2.3 e-h	63 hij
DM28	NIAB	3.5 d-g	2.4 e-h	64 hij
1021-6	NARC	4.0 def	2.7 ghi	65 hij
IR2053	KK	4.3 efg	2.8 hi	68 ijk
1053-1-2 (94)	NARC	4.8 fg	2.9 hi	68 ijk
1021-5	NARC	5.6 gh	2.5 fgh	67 ijk
4048-3	NARC	6.2 h	3.3 ij	72 ijk
50189-8-6	NARC	6.4 h	3.7 j	75 jkl
Bas 385A	NARC	6.5 h	3.7 jk	75 jkl
KS282	KK	6.9 h	4.7 l	78 lm
Bas 385	NIAB	8.4 i	5.2 l	81 lm
4439	NARC	8.8 i	5.5 l	91 m

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter do not differ significantly from each other at the 5% level. ^b KK = Kala Shah Kaku; NARC = National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad; NIAB = Nuclear Institute of Agricultural Biology, Faisalabad.

Excess water tolerance

Tolerance of rainfed lowland rice cultivars and breeding lines for submergence at seedling stage

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Submergence tolerance is a major trait needed for rice grown in submergence-prone rainfed lowland or tidal wetlands. Native rice cultivars (FR13A, FR43B) have been identified with 12 d submergence tolerance. Other cultivars (Chenab 64-117) have about 7 d submergence tolerance. But those cultivars have low yield potential. New donors and recombinant lines for improved plant type background are needed.

We screened 55 rainfed lowland rices (traditional cultivars and improved lines) in the greenhouse for tolerance for complete submergence. Seedlings were raised in 40- × 25- × 6-cm porcelain trays filled with Maahas clay soil. Ten lines, at 10 seedlings/line were maintained in each tray in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Seedlings were completely submerged 10 d after seeding (DAS) in a 150- × 150- × 45-cm artificial tank. Water depth 30 cm above the soil level, water temperature 30 °C, and light intensity 0.59 watt/m² were maintained, FR13A and IR42 were used as resistant and susceptible checks. Seedling height was measured before submergence (H_1) and after 7 d submergence (H_2). Survival was measured 5 d after the end of submergence (22 DAS). Elongation was calculated as $H_2 - H_1$ for entries with at least 20% survival.

Survival of IR43522-37-3-3 and IR40931-33-1-3-2 compared with that of resistant check FR13A (see table). Ten other lines were moderately resistant (at least 40% survival).

Survival was not correlated with initial height ($r = 0.19$) or elongation ($r = 0.01$). Most lines elongated 0.5-2.5 mm/d. Many lines with higher elongation rate had poor survival.

The excellent survival of IR43522-37-3-3-3 may be due to rapid

elongation rather than to physiological tolerance for submergence (it does not have a donor for tolerance in its parentage). IR40931-33-1-3-2 had poor elongation but excellent submergence tolerance derived from FR13A. It was selected from the cross

BKNFR76106-16-0-1-0/IR19661-131-1-2; FR13A was a parent of BKNFR76106. IR40931-33-1-3-2 has consistently shown high submergence tolerance in screening at IRRI. □

Survival after submergence and increase in seedling height of improved breeding lines and check cultivars. IRRI, 1989.

Designation	Initial plant height (H ₁) (cm)	Elongation (H ₂ -H ₁) during submergence (cm)	Survival (%)
IR43522-37-3-3-3	23.8	6.2	70
IR40931-33-1-3-2	19.3	0.7	57
FR13A (resistant check)	26.7	1.2	53
UPR238-42-2-3-1	18.7	1.2	50
IR42205-33-1-3-3-2	21.7	0.7	50
TCA4	22.3	1.2	50
LMN111	27.5	4.5	57
Patnai 23	21.7	1.8	43
TCA214	25.8	1.0	43
TCA808	25.7	0.7	40
BKNFR76106-16-0-1-0	23.3	3.3	40
TCA48	27.5	2.0	40
IR43485-22-2-2-2	19.0	3.0	40
TCA62-10	23.5	0.7	37
Baisbish	21.5	5.5	37
TCA148-3	24.8	0.5	37
IR46292-24-2-2-1-2	25.3	4.5	37
GS302	26.2	1.0	37
IR43470-7-3-5-1	21.3	1.2	33
RAUSRR 2	27.0	2.5	33
IR43049-99-23-1-1	22.8	0.7	30
IR40931-26-3-3-5	22.0	1.0	27
Madhukar	28.0	2.2	27
Jaladhi-1	20.7	1.7	27
Rupsail	21.2	0.5	23
TCA72	23.2	1.2	23
TCA62-31-1	27.5	1.8	20
IR36	21.5	7.0	20
TCA177	24.7	1.5	20
RAUSRR 8	22.7	1.0	20
IR42 (susceptible check)	19.8	1.5	20
Moddawi Karruppan	27.5	-	17
BE3	30.2	-	13
BR8	28.3	-	13
RAUSBR 80-644-1	20.0	-	13
IR43559-25-5-3-2	20.0	-	13
Nam Sagui 19	23.3	-	10
IR46298-16-3-3-3	23.5	-	10
Wagwag	25.2	-	10
TCA258	24.8	-	10
Jhingsail	19.3	-	10
TCA80-4	19.0	-	10
IR11141-6-1-4	18.7	-	10
RAUSBR 30-603-14-1-1	22.2	-	7
Mahsuri	23.0	-	3
IR40905-RRR-21	20.0	-	3
TCA 196	20.0	-	3
BR9	21.2	-	0
RAUSRR 10	18.3	-	0
Ratakuta	23.8	-	0
RAUSRR 5	25.5	-	0
TCA227	21.2	-	0
TCA279	22.3	-	0
CR1009	20.2	-	0
BR34	22.2	-	0
LSD (0.05)	0.9	1.2	10

Adverse temperature tolerance

New synthetic phytohormone analog promotes leaf photosynthetic rate of rice after chilling

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We investigated the effects of a new synthetic analog of the phytohormone abscisic acid (ABA) (developed by BASF, Ludwigshafen, FRG; coded LAB 173711) on leaf photosynthetic rate of rice plants after chilling.

ABA, LAB 173711, growth retardant tetcyclacis, and a combination of LAB 173711 and tetcyclacis were applied as a 10⁻³ mol/liter of aqueous foliar spray to IR36 plants in a controlled environment (12 h photoperiod, 26/21 °C, 70% relative humidity). At 24 h after spraying, the plants were subjected to a 2 or 3 d chilling treatment at 5 °C, kept at a transitional temperature of 23 °C for 12 h, and transferred back to the original temperature.

At 2, 9, and 24 d after chilling, net leaf photosynthetic rate was measured using a steady state CO₂/H₂O porometer (Walz, Effeltrich, West Germany) and a BINOS infrared gas analyzer (Heraeus, Hanau, West Germany).

In untreated plants, chilling caused visible injuries (leaf necrosis, death) and almost total growth cessation. Injury was still evident after 23 d recovery. Plants pretreated with